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**Title: SOP for replacing glass liner and septum and
cutting the guard column of GC Exploris**

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IMPORTANT

- Before each batch/measurement it is necessary to replace the Glass Liner and Septum to prevent contamination
- Before each batch it is recommended to cut the guard column
- When turning Off the GC: first turn off the temperature and then turn off the carrier gas flow
- When turning ON the GC: first turn on the carrier gas flow

NOTE: Turning ON/OFF GC in reverse order may cause the column destroy

Preparing GC for maintenance

- 1) Turn off the temperature (Go to Touch Screen Main Menu > Maintenance > Front (PTV) > Cool this zone > Yes > Begin Cooldown) see Figure 1.

NOTE: Front and back inlet settings can be set in the device configuration as PTV or SSL injector. This SOP describes front inlet that is set as PTV injector.

Figure 1. Touch Screen Main Menu > Maintenance

NOTE: Wait until is the temperature at least $\sim 60^{\circ}\text{C}$

- 2) Turn the carrier gas flow of front inlet Off (Instrument Control > Front Inlet (PTV) > Column flow > Off) see Figure 2.

Figure 2. PTV (Programmable Temperature Vaporizing) Injector Components
To replace the septum, Trace 1300 and TRACE 1310 Users Guide, Thermo Scientific

To replace Glass Liner and Septa

- 3) Open the flap module see Figure 3
- 4) Unscrew the Septum Cap
- 5) Remove the septum with tweezers
- 6) Unscrew the Liner Cup and using a tool to remove the old liner with liner seal (ring), see Figure 3.
- 7) Take new liner (hold only the upper part of the liner) and put liner seal (ring) to liner
- 8) Gently insert new liner with liner seal (ring) to the injector and push it gently towards the button of the injector. Hold by hand only the upper part of the liner. (Be careful not to break the glass liner).
- 9) Screw and gently tighten the Liner Cup
- 10) Place new septum and push it with fingers

11) Screw and gently tighten the septum cap

Figure 3. PTV (Programmable Temperature Vaporizing) Injector Components
To replace the septum, Trace 1300 and TRACE 1310 Users Guide, Thermo Scientific

Figure 4. The tool for liner removal is on the right & screw for opening the liner cup is on the left

To cut the guard column

- 12) Unscrew Split Nut and remove the end of the guard column with ferrule see Figure 3.
- 13) Cut 5 cm off the end of the column
- 14) Use the new ferrule and install the column back:
 - a. Insert the column through the septum (holds the nut at the position), the nut, and proper ferrule (**M4 Fittings 1/16" X 0.8mm ID (Fits 0.53 mm ID column); 20285; RESTEK**) see Figure 3.
 - b. Use a scoring wafer to remove a bit of column to make a clean, perfect-cut end and wipe the column with methanol soaked-wipe after cutting (Use a magnifying glass to check the cut, repeat it if necessary. Demand for a perfect cut here is more important than of the MS column end)
 - c. Position the column so that the end of the column extends the proper distance above the end of the ferrule (30 mm for PTV) see Figure 6.
 - d. Install the nut (do not overtighten it)

Figure 5. Inserting the column into the injector

Figure 6. Detail of the nut and column with ferrule

- 15) Turn the carrier gas on (Instrument Control > Front Inlet (PTV) > Column flow 1.2 mL/min)

Check if the gas flow gradually increases and then is constant > in system is no leak

- 16) Turn on the temperature (Maintenance > Front (PTV) > Col this zone > No > Restore temperatures
- 17) Wait minimum 30 minutes for the stabilization system